

Online Condition Monitoring Technique for Metal Oxide Surge Arresters Based on Leakage Current Components

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ABSTRACT: Metal Oxide Surge Arresters (MOSA) are connected in the system for protection of power system against over voltages. MOSA behaves as an insulator under normal working condition and offers conductive path under over voltage condition. Zinc oxide elements (ZnO Blocks) having non-linear voltage-current characteristics is used in construction of MOSA. Ageing effect under various operating conditions such as pollution, moisture ingress caused degradation of MOSA. Degradation of zinc oxide elements increase the leakage current flowing through it which can create thermal runaway conditions for MOSA. Once, it reaches to thermal runaway condition cannot return to normal working condition results in premature failure of MOSA. As MOSA constitutes a core protective device for electrical power system against transients. Condition monitoring of surge arresters should be done at periodic intervals. Online condition monitoring techniques are much popular. This paper presents the evaluation technique for MOSA based on the leakage current analysis. Maximum amplitude of total leakage current (I_T), Maximum amplitude of fundamental resistive leakage current (I_R) and maximum amplitude of third harmonic resistive leakage current (I_{3rd}) have been analysed as indicators for surge arrester condition monitoring. The ratios of these leakage current has been evaluated for to access the condition of MOSA. The obtained results are validated with other condition monitoring tests.

KEYWORDS: MOSA, over voltage, leakage current, Resistive leakage current, Third harmonic resistive leakage current.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reliable functioning of an electrical power system depends on correct operation of all its components. A substantial failure cause for failure in the power grid is lightning [1]. It is reported that lightning strikes have caused some of the largest blackouts in history [2]. Function of MOSA is to protect the power system equipment against overvoltage. Such overvoltage generated by natural lightning or switching operations in power system. MOSA consists of zinc oxide elements (ZnO) having non-linear Voltage-current characteristics. The nonlinear characteristics of ZnO is highly efficient and eliminated other types of Surge arresters in the system [3]. Lightning overvoltage cause a high peak current when it appears in an electrical circuit and MOSA provides low resistance path so as to discharge instantaneous energy to earth. Thus, MOSA limits the voltage across protected equipment to system tolerable range and avoids damage of electrical equipment. Finally, the MOSA returns to its normal condition i.e high impedance state. MOSA gets aged due to continuous operating voltage, lightning strikes, environmental pollution, temperature, humidity. This increases internal partial discharges (PD) and current flowing through it. Due to ageing effect performance of MOSA gets degrades and perform inferiorly. The inferior performance of MOSA effects protection margin and insulation coordination. If healthiness of

MOSA would not monitored at regular time interval, its degradation cannot be identified on time. Hence, Condition monitoring of MOSA is very important for safe operation of the electrical power system. As MOSAs are constructed Zinc oxide elements its equivalent circuit consists of resistive and capacitive element. The equivalent circuit of MOSA represented as non-linear resistance branch in parallel with capacitance branch as shown in Fig. 1 (a). Where, R represents the non-linear resistor and C represents capacitance. V is the voltage applied across surge arrester & total leakage current (I_T) is flowing through surge arrester. I_C and I_R are the capacitive and resistive components of total leakage current (I_T) respectively.

Fig.1: Equivalent Circuit of MOSA

The total Current (I_T) of the MOSA is given by a vector sum of a capacitive current component (I_C) and Resistive current component (I_R). Capacitive current does not vary with the degradation of the arrester and resistive component I_R which varied with degradation of MOSA [4].

$$I_T = I_R + I_C \tag{1}$$

Fig. 1 (b) shows phasor diagram of applied voltage (V), total leakage current (I_T), Resistive leakage current (I_R) and Capacitive Leakage Current (I_C). The resistive components of leakage current exceeds from its capacitive component with the rise in applied voltage [5]. Ideally the capacitance of a ZnO element in the range of 60 pF kV/cm² to 150 pF kV/cm². Which resulting in capacitive leakage current of about 0.2 mA to 3 mA under normal service condition. There is no evidence that the capacitive current would change significantly due to degradation of metal oxide resistors. Therefore measurement of capacitive current is not reliably indicator of MOSA condition. Whereas, resistive component of leakage current is sensitive indicator of change in voltage-current characteristics of metal oxide resistors. Therefore, resistive current is use as effective tool to ascertain condition of metal oxide surge arrester [6] [7]. The power loss measurement is frequently used in the laboratories but is rarely used online because simultaneous leakage current and operating voltage measurements are required [8]. In this paper new ageing criteria has been defined for MOSA. Condition monitoring technique based on leakage current measurement have been discussed. The obtained results have been validated using other offline condition monitoring techniques. Obtained results validates and proved the effectiveness of proposed technique for MOSA ageing and condition monitoring of MOSA based on leakage current measurement techniques.

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Initially condition monitoring tests on new 9 kV and 18 kV MOSA has been carried out. After initial testing both MOSAs kept in ageing process. After that all condition monitoring tests including leakage current measurement carried out on both the MOSAs. Obtained results are evaluated which are given section 4. The methodology followed has been given in figure 2.

Figure 2: Methodology

III. LABORATORY EXPERIMENTAL

Laboratory experiment on 9 kV & 18 kV metal oxide surge arrester (MOSA) was carried out Experimental set-up includes High Voltage PD free Transformer, 100 kV capacitive Voltage divider & peak volt meter, coupling capacitor, ageing ovens, Impulse current generator etc. The rating of the metal oxide surge arrester used for experiments is given in table 1 and experimental circuit has been given in figure 3.

Table 1 : Rating of MOSA

Parameter	Rating	
Rated Voltage	9 kV	18 kV
Continuous Operating Voltage	7.65	16.2
Nominal Discharge Current	5 kA	5 kA
Maximum Residual Voltage	27 kV	54 kV
External Creepage distance	240 mm	510 mm

Figure 3 : experimental circuit

Following tests have been conducted on both MOSAs.

1. Measurement of leakage currents
2. Measurement of Reference voltage at reference current
3. Measurement of partial discharge
4. Measurement of capacitance & Tan δ
5. Lightning impulse residual voltage measurement at 500 AP, 8/20 μS Impulse Current

Ageing Process of MOSA :

The ageing process followed has been given in figure 4.

Fig. 4: Ageing process of MOSA

Figure 5 : MOSA immersed in water

Resistive leakage current (IR)	135.2	276.2	104.3
Reference voltage at reference current (Vref)	18.9	17.3	8.5
Partial discharge (Pc)	1.6	1560	NA
Capacitance (pF)	51.545	51.821	0.5
Tan δ (%)	0.008356	0.02151	157.4
Lightning impulse residual voltage (kVp)	43.4	41.3	4.8

From the achieved results of various condition minoring tests, after ageing MOSA degraded. As a result of degradation leakage flowing through MOSA increased 107.55 % for 9 kV and 126.1 % for 18 kV MOSA. The resistive components of leakage current also increased 81.07 % for 9 kV and 104.3 % for 18 kV MOSA. Marginal variation in reference voltage at reference current & Impulse residual voltage is observed. The value of partial discharge quantity is also increased with increased in leakage current. Increase in value of tan δ is observed 129.90 % for 9 kV and 157.4 % for 18 kV MOSA, however value of capacitance remains almost same. It can be seen that total leakage current, resistive leakage current and tan δ value increased substantially after ageing. Variation in measured parameters for 9 kV and 18 kV MOSA have been given in figure 7 and figure 8 respectively.

Figure 6 : MOSA under salt fog

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Obtained results of all the tests on new MOSAs and after ageing have been recorded and analyzed. The comparison of before and after ageing for 9 kV and 18 kV MOSA has been given in table 2 and table 3 respectively.

Table 2: Experimental results for 9 kV MOSA

Rating of Surge Arrester : 9 kV			
Parameter	Before Ageing	After Ageing	% Variation
Total leakage current, (IT)	405.3	841.2	107.5
Resistive leakage current (IR)	155.3	281.2	81.1
Reference voltage at reference current (Vref)	10.1	9.1	-9.9
Partial discharge (Pc)	1.5	105	NA
Capacitance (pF)	52.102	50.712	2.7
Tan δ (%)	0.009241	0.021245	129.9
Lightning impulse residual voltage (kVp)	23.5	20.12	14.4

Figure 7 : Variation in measured parameters in %

Table 2: Experimental results for 18 kV MOSA

Rating of Surge Arrester : 18 kV			
Parameter	Before Ageing	After Ageing	% Variation
Total leakage current, (IT)	443.2	1002.1	126.1

Figure 8 : Variation in measured parameters in %

V. CONCLUSION

It is very important to check health of MOSA at regular interval. Online methods are preferred. Due to ageing effect leakage current flowing through MOSA increases which increase power loss. Resistive component of leakage current increases substantially. Total leakage current includes external leakage current & internal leakage current flowing through surge arresters. Due to pollution external surface leakage current increased, which shows higher leakage current. To avoid effect of external leakage current measurement of resistive leakage current is most suitable technique for condition monitoring of surge arresters. With increase in resistive leakage current, partial discharge quantity and $\tan \delta$ also increases in linearly. The value of capacitance does not shows variation, however value of $\tan \delta$ increased after ageing effect, which may be due to moisture penetration. Hence, measurement of resistive leakage is useful technique to check the healthiness of MOSA.

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